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ABŪ BAKR AL-KĀSĀNĪ'S WORK "BADĀ'Ī' AL-ŞANĀ'Ī' FĪ TARTĪB ASH-SHARĀ'Ī'" IN THE WORK OF THE UNIQUE METHODS OF SORTING FIQH RULES

Qambarov A'zam Muxammadali o'g'li

International Islamic academy of Uzbekistan
Senior teacher of Islamic studies and study of
Islamic civilization ICESCO chair
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ABSTRACT. The opinions expressed in the article are formulated in accordance with the requirements of the methodological principles and traditional methods of the Ḥanafī faith. Opinions on social welfare are observed on the basis of modern standards based on the book "Badā'ī' al-şanā'ī' fī tartīb al-sharā'ī'" written by the jurist of Samarkand, Abū Bakr al-Kāsānī, and based on the jurisprudence rules and legal arguments introduced in Central Asia in general, in particular in our Republic.

Key words: Badā'ī', Şanā'ī', Kāsān, farḍ, wajib, sunnah, evidence, ijmā', qiyās, asl, 'Uşūl, furu', permissible, Islām, sharī'ah.

The researcher scientist Fadwa 'Abd al-'Ālim Aḥmad At-Toyyari focuses on revealing the peculiarities of Abū Bakr al-Kāsānī's methods of arranging fiqh rules in the work "Badā'ī' al-şanā'ī' fī tartīb al-sharā'ī'" in the scientific research work entitled "Corrections of Imām al-Kāsānī in the work "Badā'ī' al-şanā'ī'". Below are the notable aspects of Fadwa 'Abd al-'Ālim Aḥmad At-Tayyari's work:

"Imām al-Kāsānī's corrections in the book of hunts and slaughtered animals."

It contains four matlabs, the first of which is:

A sign that determines whether a fish that floats to the surface is edible or not.

1. Edit the disputed positions in this issue:

There is no disagreement among the scholars regarding the halalness of eating caught fish, as it is blessed in Surah al-Māida verse 96.: "

أَجَلٌ لَّكُمْ صَيْدُ الْبَحْرِ وَطَعَامُهُ مَتَاعًا لَّكُمْ وَلِلسَّيَّارَةِ وَحُرِّمَ عَلَيْكُمْ صَيْدُ الْبَرِّ مَا دُمْتُمْ حُرْمًا وَاتَّقُوا اللَّهَ الَّذِي
إِلَيْهِ تُحْشَرُونَ.

"Lawful to you is the pursuit of water-game and its use for food for the benefit of yourselves and those who travel; but forbidden is the pursuit of land-game: as long as ye are in the Sacred Precincts or in pilgrim garb. And fear God to whom ye shall be gathered back!"¹

¹ Sheikh 'Abd al-'Azīz Maṣṣūr. Translation and interpretation of the meanings of the Holy Qur'ān. Tafsir-books – Tashkent - 2023. – P. 124.

“In our Ḥanafī Madhhab, it is permissible to eat only fish from aquatic animals. Only a fish that has died for no reason (and is upside down) is not eaten (Books Al- Hidāyah, "Al-Iḥtiyār").”²

In a ḥadīth narrated by Jābir ibn ‘Abd Allāh, may Allah be pleased with him, the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, said: عَنْ جَابِرِ بْنِ عَبْدِ اللَّهِ قَالَ: قَالَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ: مَا أَلْقَى الْبَحْرُ أَوْ جَزَرَ عَنْهُ فَكُلُوهُ وَمَا مَاتَ فِيهِ وَطَفَا فَلَا تَأْكُلُوهُ. رَوَاهُ أَبُو دَاوُدَ وَابْنُ مَاجَةَ وَالدَّارَقُطْنِيُّ.

Jābir ibn ‘Abd Allāh, may God bless him and grant him peace, narrates from the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace: "Eat what the sea casts out (to the shore) or what remains on the shore when the water recedes. But do not believe that he died without an external cause and rose to the surface of the water" (narration of Abū Dāwūd, Ibn Mājah and Dāraqūṭnī).

This is what the jurists of our sect said about this:

يُؤْكَلُ الْأَصْلُ فِي إِبَاحَةِ السَّمَكِ إِنْ مَاتَ بِأَفَةٍ يُؤْكَلُ وَمَا مَاتَ بِغَيْرِ أَفَةٍ لَا.

“ The original rule regarding the halal of fish is that it is permissible to eat it if it has died due to some external calamity. It is not permissible to eat it if he died without an accident or external cause" ("Radd al-muḥtār", vol. 5, p. 248.)³

There is a difference between the opinions of popular scholars and scholars of the Ḥanafī school about eating fish that have floated to the surface of the water. Public scientists say that it is permissible to eat such fish.

According to the Ḥanafī school of thought, it is forbidden to eat fish that has floated to the surface of the water. Another point on which the Ḥanafī school disagreed about the fish floating on the surface of the water is whether the fish is on its back or dead. The first difference that a fish is on its back is that the fish is not dead, it may have come to the surface due to an accident, or it may have suffocated due to lack of air.

The second difference in the cause of death of the fish is that it did not die without incident, regardless of whether it floated to the surface or not.

These two differences are the basis of the disputes in this matter.

The scholars of the Ḥanafī school differed on two points, the first is that the fish that died due to an unknown event, regardless of whether they floated to the surface of the water or not, belong to one category, i.e. non-halal (unlawful dead). Second, fish that float to the surface are still considered dead, whether

²Is it possible to eat dead fish in a container? #ҳалол_ҳаром. Fatvo.uz. 25.08.2021. https://www.facebook.com/diniysavollar/posts/355463149643474/?locale=ms_MY
https://www.facebook.com/diniysavollar/?_ft_n=AZWEIFc0oi9K6XDmJoMRuD8Y524ylOQul4ubKbr0gaxvvKotjiDfs5wsQZk82aNJeTF0u-LCbG4BlqW7C6rd4U1mto2VjDfoccDz_9ypu4C5ZctEPJGg-cl6eHE7z51-DkKVznWBJUDrJqvypWli4iBORjYslvksePFIVJxtUVg&_tn=-UC%2CP-R

³ Muslim Board of Uzbekistan Fatwa Center.FATVO.UZ. <https://t.me/s/Diniysavollar?before=5475>

due to an accident or suffocation. Some of the scholars of the Ḥanafī sect are of the same opinion.

If it is said that a fish that has floated to the surface of the water is a fish that has floated to the surface of the water in a dead state, and it is treated that it does not matter for what reason it died, then it is considered that it is not permissible to eat that fish, and therefore a dead fish is not eaten; because a fish that floats to the surface of the water is considered dead, so a dead fish is not permissible according to the Hanafis.

If a fish that floats to the surface of the water is called a fish that died a natural death, not as a result of an event or external influence, then it is not permissible, and it is not permissible to eat the dead fish. It doesn't matter if it pops up or not. Such a fish is not considered to have been killed by an incident, it is considered *muboh* and can be eaten.

This is the root of the original issue in jurisprudence, and it is the ruling of a fish that floats to the surface of the water. The scholars of Ḥanafī jurisprudence have two opinions when it comes to this matter, but their *isnads* are not mentioned.

I will try to find a source that can be used as an *isnad* for both of these points and I will say:

To prove the first opinion (this is the opinion that a fish that floats to the surface of the water is a fish that has died naturally, regardless of whether it floated to the surface of the water or not, and not because of any external influence or event...) According to some of the Sharī'ah proofs that can be obtained, it is *haram* to eat the flesh of a dead animal. Including dead fish meat. It is based on the content of the verse of Allah Almighty: "حُرِّمَتْ عَلَيْكُمْ الْمَيْتَةُ" - "Forbidden to you (for food) are: dead meat".

The aspect of quoting Allah's verse as evidence is as follows: The reason why Allah has forbidden His servants to eat the meat of dead animals is that eating such meat causes blood diseases for the human body, as well as harms his religion and body.

Among the sea fish, it is permissible to eat the flesh of the fish that floats to the surface of the water and it is forbidden to eat it. The flesh of the fish that comes out of it is permissible because it is not clear how the fish died, but if it is clear how it died or was killed, it follows that eating it is not permissible..

Regarding the argument that can be the basis of the second opinion (this opinion is about the fact that the fish floated to the surface of the water

regardless of how it died): not only fish in this case, but also any animals are included in the category of dead, and the flesh of any dead animal is not eaten.

Superiority: The first of these two views is superior because the description given to the fish that floated to the surface of the water is based on the cause of the death of the fish. In Mubo, if the cause of death of fish is known, then the fish is not included in this category, but if the cause of death is unknown, it is included in this category, that is, in the category of dead fish, because the sign of the cause of death narrows the scope of consumption of the fish and expands its scope. The fact that the prohibitions in the limitation of the cause of death of the fish, the certainty of the death or the permission in the limitation of the mubah, is a factor that sheds light on the question of its indeterminacy. is in accordance with Sharī'ah evidence. Allah is the most knowledgeable.

The second matlab: Jallala judgments about the use of animals

1-Editing Disputes:

Jallala: "Jallala" are animals that are used to eating impure things and excrement, and because of eating a lot of them, both themselves and their milk are putrid. The scholars of the sect said that it is not halal to eat the meat and drink the milk of a "jallala" animal, whose food consists of all or most of the unclean things, but if those animals are tied up and fed with clean suckers for a certain period of time, then it is permissible to eat their meat and drink their milk. Some say that an animal whose meat and milk have a foul smell is "jellala".

According to the Sharī'ah, it is forbidden to eat the meat of the "jallala", drink its milk, ride on it according to the ḥadīth of our prophet. But if he ibn ds the animals, gives them clean feed, takes care of them and removes their dirt, it becomes halal. Then he can drink their meat and milk and ride himself.

There is a difference of opinion as to whether jallala can be used only by eating the meat of animals and not drinking their milk.

Some people are of the opinion that as long as the above features exist, such animals cannot be used until they are tied up, given clean food, and taken care of to remove their impurities.

Others say that it is permissible to use such animals, even if they are not fed and fed. However, since there are ḥadīths about the fact that the unclean and unclean things they eat are absorbed into their bodies and skin, and because of the foul odors emanating from their mouths, bodies, and excrement, they can cause discomfort and even damage to the health of people around them, so it is correct to use these animals even in farm work won't be.

Based on this, the causes of conflict are as follows:

Two sayings on this matter are the reason for the origin of disputes:

The first sentence: It is not halal to feed jalala animals until they have been tied up and used until their odor is removed.

According to the narration of Muḥammad ibn Al- Ḥasan, this rule came from Imām Abū Ḥanīfa (r.a.) and Qādī Isbijabi and Al- Ḥakīm Ash-Shahīd said it is permissible.

The second argument: it is possible to use such animals without being tied up, as long as they do not smell bad, but there is also an opinion that if they smell bad, then they cannot be used and this idea is found in Al- Qudūrī ⁴ and As-Sarakhsī ⁵

Al-Kāsānī, comparing these two opinions in terms of superiority, says: " وَمَا ذَكَرَ الْقُدُورِيُّ رَحْمَةً اللَّهِ أَجْوَدٌ " (The one mentioned by Al- Qudūrī, may God have mercy on him, is the best.)

Third: Effect of conflict:

The effect of the conflict is shown in the fact that if it is used from a noble animal, the smell does not spread.

According to the first qawl: It is not halal to use Jallala unless it is fed with pure suckling for a certain number of days.

According to the second sentence: It is lawful to use it.

Fourth: Evidence:

The arguments of those who say the first sentence are two, the first is the evidence of effect, and it is also of two kinds:

1- Ḥadīths prohibiting the use of noble animals: for example: ‘Amr ibn Shu‘ayb narrated a ḥadīth from his father, and his father from his father: "The Messenger of Allah (pbuh) forbade eating the meat of donkeys on the Day of Khaibar and riding sacred animals and eating their meat ."

In another ḥadīth narrated by Ibn Abbas: "The Messenger of Allah (pbuh) forbade riding animals."

In another recorded ḥadīth: "The Messenger of Allah (pbuh) forbade riding them for Hajj and Umrah, using their meat for food or using them in cases other than these conditions."

⁴ Aḥmad ibn Muḥammad ibn Aḥmad ibn Ja'far ibn Hamdan Al- Qudūrī (born in Baghdad in 362 AH and died in Baghdad in 428) is a Hanafī jurist. His book "Mukhtasar al-Qudūrī" is famous.

⁵ Muḥammad ibn Aḥmad ibn Abū Sahl Abū Sarakhsī title Shamsul Aimmā, judge, mujtahid jurist with great influence among Hanafī scholars, mutakallim scholar. He is from the people of Sarakhs (Khorasan) and his most famous work is "Al-Mabsut" which consists of 30 juz and is devoted to issues of jurisprudence and sharī'ah. Accused of speaking against the Khagan, he was imprisoned in the city of Uzgan, then after his release, he lived in Ferghana and died in 483 AH.

Evidence from these ḥadīths: Prohibition of eating the meat of Jallalah animals and riding them.

2- ḥadīths that show that it is necessary to tie them and clean them before using them, for example: in a ḥadīth narrated from ‘Abd Allāh ibn ‘Amr, he says: "The Messenger of Allah (pbuh) did not eat the meat of camels, drink their milk, carry loads on them, ride them. they forbade them until they were tied up for forty days and nights and fed with pure suckling, except for black (domestic camels) camels.

Evidential aspect: It is permissible to use them on the condition that they are fed without causing suffering and harm to people.

The second argument is a mental argument, and it has two ways:

1. Comparison between the prohibition of use and the prohibition of eating its flesh and drinking its milk. Thus, it is an abomination to eat the flesh and drink the milk of the nobles until they are tied up and fed with pure suckling. Also, they cannot be used until they are tied. This prohibition is a ḥadīth narrated by Ibn Umar, who says: "The Messenger of Allah (pbuh) forbade eating the meat of animals and drinking their milk."

Al-Kāsānī says: "If one relies on the prevailing opinion that their meat changes and becomes foul because they eat unclean things, then eating them as foul-smelling (if smelly) food is makruh, so their use is the same."

2-second way: Iktiron is a way of proving (proving facts based on their interrelationship), in which several ḥadīths narrated by the predecessors include the prohibition of eating the meat and drinking the milk of noble animals; that these prohibitions are also prohibitions against riding them and using them in similar activities; This argument is based on the same ruling that it is not permissible to eat their meat and drink their milk until they have been tied up for a certain number of days, fed with clean fodder, and cleansed by drinking clean water. Here is an example of this.

The evidence of those who said the second sentence, i.e. (If one eats something that removes its stench, it can be used, but if it smells bad, it cannot be used to avoid suffering and harm to people) has the following evidence:

– Jallalah is prohibited from eating the meat and drinking the milk of animals because their meat also becomes smelly if used and therefore it is forbidden to eat it. This ruling is a ruling in the category of "maqulul ma'an" (the meaning derived from the mind), and such rulings oscillate between existence and non-existence. Therefore, it is permissible to eat their meat if they are arrested and treated with clean suckling. The order of this will be the same. The

evil of forbidding Jallalah without causing it to be used for riding or similar activities is with its meat and milk. If it itself becomes foul and emits a smell when applied to the surroundings, riding it is not possible because it causes suffering to people.

Al-Kāsānī says: "...the meaning of this return is not related to his breed, but to his emerging gem; Because its use was halal in nature, so this prohibition arises only because it has changed from its original nature to a different state."⁶

- The prohibition that comes from the analogy of riding is the prohibition of eating its meat and drinking its milk. Hence, there is no harm in riding them, even eating their meat and drinking their milk; Harm from their use comes from the clause "bad smell", but until then there was no harm and no obligation to feed.

Fifth: Superiority - The second sentence is superior because it refers to the meaning derived from the mind, and according to it there is no harm in using and riding animals that do not emit stench. Allah is the most knowledgeable."⁷

If we come to the aspect that Fadwa ‘Abd al-‘Ālim Aḥmad At-Toyyari pays attention to in his scientific research work entitled "Imām al-Kāsānī's corrections in the work "Badā’i’ al-ṣanā’i’ fī tartīb al-sharā’i’", it is noticeable that the scientist understood the essence of al-Kāsānī's research method.

Dr. At-Toyyari explains the materials arranged in these books in the work without neglecting their origins and fars, qiyas and istihsan. After summarizing the methodical and Furu'i rules on the issue of halal or haram of fish floating on the surface of the water, he gives the final conclusion that "According to the beliefs of the Ḥanafī sect, eating fish floating on the surface of the water is haram."

In the next issue, which is called Jallala's Rulings on the Use of Animals, Dr. At-Tayyari directly quotes Al-Kāsānī's views in two places.

1- " Al-Kāsānī says: "If one relies on the prevailing opinion that their meat will change and become smelly because they eat unclean things, then eating them as a smelly (if smelly) food is makruh, so their use is the same."

2- Al-Kāsānī says: "...the meaning of this return is not related to his breed, but to his emerging gem; Because its use was inherently halal, so this prohibition arises only because it has changed from its original characteristic (honesty)."⁸

⁶ al-Kāsānī Abū Bakr (Alouddin). Badā’i’ al-ṣanā’i’ fī tartīb al-sharā’i’. – V:10. – P.140.

⁷ Fadwa ‘Abd al-‘Ālim Aḥmad At-Tayyari. Corrections of Imām al-Kāsānī in "Badā’i’ al-ṣanā’i’".E/mail: fadwaa44@gmail.com

⁸ al-Kāsānī Abū Bakr (Alouddin). Badā’i’ al-ṣanā’i’ fī tartīb al-sharā’i’. – V:10. – P.140.

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Badr ibn Rashid Oli Abdil Latif uses a unique method in researching the material in this work in his scientific work entitled "Fiqh Rules⁹ in Al-Kāsānī's "Badā'us Sanāi".

The scientist names the subject under investigation, gives methodological rules about it, and then returns to the interpretation of the meaning of those rules, citing al-Kāsānī's verbal propositions. In doing so, he summarizes the lexical and terminological definitions given by fiqh scholars to a specific word in the process of elucidating the content of each lexical unit in the text of the rule and provides sources of quotations from them.

A review of the literature on fiqh knowledge shows that the books of furu' al-fiqh were the primary sources in the early periods, but in later periods these rules became independent subjects.

In jurisprudential works, the fact that the religious scholars used the rules in their own way in order to justify their theories (schools) in order to support their madhhabs is of great importance in enriching the terminology of Furu'. The study of the development process of the science of Islamic law and the study of individual jurisprudence issues based on the casuistic method shows that the science of jurisprudence has emerged as an independent science.

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⁹ Badr bin Roshid Oli Abdil Latif. Saudiya Arabistoni. Ar-Riyoz. Imom Muhammad bin Sa'ud nomidagi Islom Universiteti. Shariat fakul'teti. 1428 – 1429 هـ القواعد الشرعية في كتاب بدائع الصنائع للكاساني (ت. 587هـ). بدر بن راشد آل عبد اللطيف 1428 – 1429 هـ. C:\Users\user\Desktop\Badr bin Roshid Oli Abdil Latif